

ENRICH IN AFRICA

D4.3 Research Briefs

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About EiA: Funded by the European Union (Horizon 2020 programme), ENRICH in Africa is a project designed to bring together core stakeholders from both regions, in order to support and strengthen the European and African innovation ecosystem.

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Abstract

The current social and economic environment of African economies – surrounded by myriad of challenges such as natural resource dependency and growing young population that is unemployed is a breeding ground for innovative startups. The unemployed can find employment by starting businesses around value adding activities to the natural resources, and solving myriad of local problems in health, agriculture and environment. Luckily many governments have realized the potential of entrepreneurship and startups in addressing African challenges, and have put in place various policies and programs to nurture the startups. Using entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem framework, this paper analyses the status and challenges around the formation of growth oriented startups in five African countries. Methodologically, the work largely relied on existing information, supplemented with interview of some selected important system actors in the five countries.

The findings indicates that, the five countries – and Africa more generally – have some serious challenges around important system actors and functions that enable a strong entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem, such as availability of funds, knowledge generating institutions such as universities, experienced human resources, capable incubators and accelerators, culture, local corporations, angel investors, venture capitalists, government policies and business environment, and weak interaction between and among these system elements. Finally, the paper provides some policy proposals on how the challenges can be addressed, on top being good policies that are implemented and conducive business environment. Given the scarcity of in-depth and high quality studies around Africa’s entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems, the proposal is also made for further research around the system actors, especially the linkage between startups and knowledge generating institutions.

1. Introduction – Background and objectives

This research paper on entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem is the analysis of the outcome of the mapping exercise which was carried out in the five African markets, namely Tanzania, South Africa, Ghana, Senegal and Zimbabwe. The mapping exercise is one of the tasks in the work packages of the ENRICH in Africa project. The mandate of this project is to facilitate entrepreneurship and innovation in Africa and Europe through ecosystem building, especially through enabling networking between and among entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem actors. The project is intended to provide a strong and holistic EU-Africa innovation ecosystem that ensures the work done within the innovation spaces such as the incubators and accelerators builds innovative potential of productive entrepreneurs, and is sustainable and integrated into the wider economic landscape of these countries and the two regions. Specifically:

- Map existing entrepreneurial infrastructure and services, with a focus on scaling and innovation.
- Map support needs and gaps of innovative entrepreneurs within the selected African and European markets and their connectivity to global markets and vice versa (support needs and gaps of European entrepreneurs planning to scale to target markets) in order to inform services of Enrich in Africa and the EiA champions in a needs-based way and identify opportunity points for EiA and policymakers – what policies need to be put in place and what needs to be strengthened.

To understand the current status, challenges and opportunities in regard to the above issues, the mapping exercise was carried out in the five mentioned markets. Specifically the mapping exercises served to identify strength and weaknesses of the ecosystems in these markets, basically to understand the extent to which the markets have sufficient system elements and actors to support growth of productive entrepreneurship. In so doing the major task is to identify gaps in the system, including the level of linkage among system actors. The policy objective is to direct the service provision of ENRICH in Africa's Champions and to provide evidence for policy that provides a conducive environment for the growth and innovativeness of startups - both in Africa and Europe.

In terms of the structure of the report, section two that follows this introductory remark will be on conceptual framework on entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem that guided the mapping exercise, whereas section three is on methodology. Section four provides outcome of the mapping for each of the five markets, in a nutshell. The mapping for each of the markets is preceded by some basic social and economic information for each market. Sections five pulls the mapping exercise of the five countries together – with additional information from other African countries, with the objective to paint a rough picture for the whole of Africa. Section six provides some concluding remarks and recommendations.

2. Conceptual Framework

This section presents an analytical framework to be used to analyze the entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem in any country. It defines important concepts such as entrepreneurship and its ecosystems; how entrepreneurship is related to start-ups and innovation, and therefore coining the concept of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems; and what it takes to have a strong entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem in a given social and economic context.

2.1 Definition of concepts

Innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystems have recently attracted the enormous attention of policymakers, business practitioners and academia. This is because of the indisputable role both the entrepreneur and innovation plays in development. The concept of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems involves three major things: entrepreneurship, innovation and ecosystems. The concept of ecosystems is popularly used either for entrepreneurship or for innovation independently; but sometimes it is combined, resulting in the concept of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems. This work makes use of the combined concept in its analysis. For clarity, we first define individual concepts.

2.2 Entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial ecosystem

The concept of entrepreneurship has been defined slightly differently by different people. For instance, for Stevenson and Mossi (1986) entrepreneurship is the process of creating value by bringing together a unique combination of resources to exploit an opportunity. This means entrepreneurs are those people who are good at identifying social and economic opportunities. While entrepreneurship is largely understood in economic terms, there are those that are good at identifying and working on social opportunities. In this report, we are largely concerned with economic entrepreneurship. Defined in economic terms, for Low and Macmillan (1988), entrepreneurship is the creation of a new business. The difference between the two definitions is emphasis on uniqueness of combination of resources, signaling innovativeness in Steven and Mossi's definition. Others have indeed defined entrepreneurship in terms of innovativeness in exploiting an economic opportunity, rather than just creating any new business. Schumpeter is the first to bring entrepreneurship and innovation together. According to Schumpeter (1934), entrepreneurship is making new combinations, which include the introduction of new goods, new methods of production, opening of new markets, new sources of supply and new organizations, which is precisely how innovation is defined – as we can shortly see. For Kuratko and Hodgetts (2001), entrepreneurship is a process of innovation and new venture creation through four major dimensions, namely individual, organizational, environmental, and process. The difference between Schumpeter's definition and Kuratko and Hodgetts is that while for Schumpeter, entrepreneurship happens even in large and established firms – as long as they are coming up with new things, for Kuratko and Hodgetts, it has to be establishment of a new and an innovative firm. Analyzing all these definitions and taking into account that our work is concerned with small firms – especially start-ups, we take entrepreneurship (in this context) to

be the establishment of new and growing ventures. The term growing here takes into account innovation, because without innovation, growth of a venture is difficult to achieve.

Important in entrepreneurship is the concept of entrepreneurial ecosystem, which connotes the fact that no entrepreneur starts and grows a business alone. Accordingly, at the centre of the entrepreneurial ecosystem are the necessary actors with all their interactions and relationships. These relationships among actors support entrepreneurial activities. The actors are normally located within geographically bounded social and economic contexts. The entrepreneurship ecosystem is not a static system, but rather evolves along with changes in social and economic contexts. According to Ianioglo (ND), entrepreneurial ecosystems are evolving through the interactions between actors, where the dynamics depend on factors of national and international order, as well as cultural specificities in a given locality. Within this broader understanding of systemic and context specificity of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, is specific definition of entrepreneurial ecosystem, where many have defined it slightly differently. According to Stam(2015), the entrepreneurial ecosystem is a set of interdependent actors and factors coordinated in such a way that they enable productive entrepreneurship. For Mack and Mayer (2016), entrepreneurial ecosystems consist of interacting components, which foster new firm formation and associated regional entrepreneurial activities, while for Audretsch & Belitski (2017), entrepreneurial ecosystems are institutional and organizational as well as other systemic factors that interact to influence identification and commercialization of entrepreneurial opportunities. In short, entrepreneurial ecosystem is that system of actors and factors that together influence the activities of productive entrepreneurship that foster new firms formation and growth.

2.3 Innovation and innovation ecosystem, and how it relates to entrepreneurial ecosystem

The essence of innovation is novelty; it is generally understood as putting new ideas and knowledge into practical use such as marketing of new products and widespread use of new processes in economic units. Specifically, according to the Oslo manual, 4th edition (OECD 2018), innovation is a new or improved product or process (or combination thereof) that differs significantly from the unit's previous products or processes and that has been made available to potential users (product) or brought into use by the unit (process). This is a general definition of innovation – whether or not it is in economic terms. In economic terms more specifically, the manual define innovation as a new or improved product or business process (or combination thereof) that differs significantly from the firm's previous products or business processes and that has been introduced on the market or brought into use by the firm.

Just like entrepreneurship, innovation requires a system of interacting actors in a given geographical boundary under social and economic context; it is also a dynamic concept. Specifically, innovation ecosystem is “the evolving set of actors, activities, and artefacts, and the institutions and relations, including complementary and substitutionary relations that are important for the innovative performance of an actor or a population of actors” (O. Granstrand, & M. Holgersson, 2020).

So how is the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem related? First we must bear in mind that, whether it is entrepreneurship or innovation, a key feature in the concept of ecosystem is interaction of actors - whether just an entrepreneur, large and established or small firms and startups, entrepreneurs do not just compete with each other using their own resources, but cooperate, interact and use shared resources, knowledge, networks, infrastructure and support to co-create value (Lanioglo ND). This means that all the important actors for both the entrepreneurship and innovation must interact to create value or bring forth innovation.

Regarding entrepreneurship, what is important is *productive entrepreneurship*, which is that does not only start firms but manages them to growth. This is because most startups remain small or disappear like – as we shall shortly see – what is being witnessed in most Africa countries. Therefore, productive entrepreneurship must always include growth and sustainability of startups: According to (Davidsson, Achtenhagen, and Naldi 2007) because most of the start-ups remain very small for their entire existence, it is wise to include aspects of early growth in defining productive entrepreneurship, and there are system elements that are required for this growth. So for productive entrepreneurship we have two interacting sub-systems: the one that enables establishment of productive firms, and the one that helps them to grow. We know that firms can hardly grow without innovation as defined in this work, and therefore the system that helps startups to grow is indeed an innovation ecosystem; and therefore some people when they talk of entrepreneurial ecosystem, they mean the one that overlaps with innovation ecosystem. However, care must be taken, because according to many scholars (e.g. Lanioglo, ND), not all entrepreneurs innovate. For this reason, for making reference to good productive entrepreneurship, it is important to use concepts of entrepreneurship and innovation together, and therefore coining the concept of entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem. This system that combines entrepreneurship and innovation performs a number of functions, which together enables productive entrepreneurship. According to many scholars (see for instance e.g. Lanioglo, ND), important functions depends on a given social and economic context, but following seem to be cutting across many contexts; and it is these on which we focus our analysis for this paper:

- ❖ **Policy:** Entrepreneurship depends on a context that is shaped by governments through policy and enabling environment; and policies may encourage or hinder entrepreneurship. Efficient policies endeavor to develop the ecosystem by building capabilities of individual actors and facilitate the interactive linkage and learning among system actors.
- ❖ **Finance:** Providing traditional and alternative sources of finance, e.g. microloans, bank loans, business angels, seed investors, venture capital, grants, etc
- ❖ **Human Capital:** Accessible skilled labour is a driver of success in the modern knowledge economy. Workers should have skills, abilities and expertise that meet the specific demand of enterprises
- ❖ **Access to Markets:** Access to markets – both local and global – is essential to any enterprise. Customers with their needs create opportunities for entrepreneurship; and without demanding customers, there will be no innovation and thriving enterprises.

- ❖ **Culture:** To what extent people value entrepreneurs in a given cultural setting. Here we can look at things such as widespread training of entrepreneurship; cultivating a culture of people valuing starting a business rather than being employed; high respect for successful entrepreneurs, and the like.
- ❖ **Support Systems:** Apart from physical infrastructure such as transportation, energy and telecommunications, a strong entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem normally consist of some necessary actors and elements, which interact and learn from each other so as to take an entrepreneur through the whole “innovation pipeline”, from ideation and prototype development, to market testing (proof of concept), to growth stage and scale to reach new markets (HDIF, ND). In the following paragraphs we briefly describe these important actors for innovative start-ups. These are:

i) Research and development institutions, including higher learning institutions

Research Institutions are crucial for fledgling innovation due to their role in knowledge creation and diffusion, and are a primary tool for governments seeking to spur research and innovation in their economies. They are in most cases sources of innovative ideas for starting and growing businesses. They are also sources of human resources for innovative companies. So for any startup or innovative company, strong link with these organizations is absolutely necessary.

ii) Incubators and Accelerators

Incubators and accelerators play an important role in the innovation ecosystem in providing a supportive environment for startups and companies. The two structures have slightly different roles in startups, while incubators focus more on the early stage of product development for ventures that do not yet have a business model, accelerators concentrate on those ventures that already have a business model; they therefore focus on speeding up the growth of startups. But typically both of them endeavor to provide a physical space for innovators to convene and share ideas while benefiting from shared technology infrastructure and equipment. They also often provide entrepreneurs with access to a network of business and technical advisors / mentors capable of providing guidance and assistance in product development, finance, business planning, marketing, legal consulting, manufacturing, etc.

iii) Private Corporations

One of the very important actor in the startups ecosystem is large companies¹. Corporations associate with startups either through partnerships, equity investments, or accelerator programs, allowing them to make use of the disruptive ideas and innovation startups can bring to their organization. Additionally, corporations often pay more to their employees who in turn open startups since they have saved enough money working and gaining expertise in a corporation as a result, many new startups emerge to support these corporations, like inputs and service

¹<https://www.startupblink.com/blog/the-impact-of-corporations-on-startup-ecosystems/>

providers, co-working chains, logistical support. And corporations themselves benefits from startups because of the disruptive and innovative nature of startups that can help resolve internal business issues, provide entry into newer markets and technology, or keep them updated on our changing times.

iv) Angel investors

Angel Investors play an important role in helping startups to overcome common funding gaps between stage two of proof of concept and transition to scale. They are often less risk averse than Venture Capitalists and can sometimes directly advance innovations by taking a position on the board of the start-up, assisting its management with their own knowledge and experience while also widening the range of contacts and networks that the firm needs to secure additional supporters and follow-on financing.

v) Venture capitalists

A venture capitalist is an investor who either provides capital to startup ventures or supports small companies that wish to expand and scale, but do not have access to equities markets. Venture capitalists are willing to invest in such companies because they can earn a massive return on their investments if these companies are a success

vi) Governments

The role of government in innovation is through provision of a conducive business environment and incentive and regulatory framework that facilitate establishment and growth of innovative businesses. Establishing flourishing interactive linkage among system actors is one of the major roles of governments.

vii) Startups themselves

Startups and entrepreneurs need to be connected to themselves for the purpose of learning from each other.

3. Methodology

Much of the information for this work has been drawn from the individual mapping exercise of the five markets – itself largely depending on existing information: the work is largely a desk top research, complemented by some primary information.

Secondary

For secondary information, three types of literature were reviewed: First is that which explains the social and economic context of each of the five markets – to paint the picture within which the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem sits within these markets. The second type is on the past studies/mapping, specifically searching for the existing information on the status of the

six framework conditions or functions of the entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem that are identified under section two on conceptual framework, which are: policy environment, finance, culture, support system, human resources and access to markets – basically targeting the gaps in terms of adequacy of the actors and their functions, their capabilities and interaction. The third source of literature is policy documents. The search included websites of important actors, e.g. policy and regulatory related organizations, general Google search by the use of the key words that include the six framework elements/functions. The third strand of literature is targeted at extent to which policy and regulatory frameworks are either supportive or working against the ecosystems.

Primary

The identified gaps in literature were filled through primary tools such as interviews of key actors and focus group discussions.

Limitations for the study

There were some limitations that might have affected the findings of this study – both for the secondary and primary information. For the secondary information, much of the sources are not from rich in-depth research reports and papers, but from website blogs that to a large extent is from experiences of the individual practitioners, rather than from a comprehensive data collected from a sample that is representative. However, the volume and diversity of these sources in itself is a good alternative to in-depth research. For the primary data, the project partners spoke to only few in the system actors. However, because these are well selected individuals who – given their positions – are expected to know the working of the system in individual countries, their views are taken to adequately represent views of the rest of the system actors.

4. Findings

As explained in the introductory section, this part will presented country wise – starting with general country characteristics such as the size of the country, population, country GDP, GDP per capita, life expectancy, unemployment status, education structure and levels, expenditure in R&D as percentage of GDP, ICT infrastructure, number of startups per year and survival rates, where available, before moving into analyzing the adequacy of the identified framework condition/ functions of the entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem actors identified in the conceptual framework.

4.1 Tanzania

4.1.1 Social and Economic context

The United Republic of Tanzania has a relatively large population estimated to be 62 million people². This makes Tanzania the 24th largest country in the world by population – larger than South Africa and slightly smaller than Italy³. The country's growth has been propelled by various sectors including transportation, infrastructure projects, communications, agriculture, manufacturing, renewable sources of electricity, wholesale and retail trade, travel and tourism, real estate, and business services.

The country's impressive growth dropped to 4.3% in 2021 because of COVID-19 pandemic. In 2022, a slight increase in GDP growth to 4.6% from 4.3% in 2021 was projected. In addition, the International Labour Organization (ILO) estimates shows that the unemployment rate in Tanzania was approximately 2.7% in 2021⁴ and per capita income of approximately USD 1,073 according to the World Bank.

The numbers above are hand in hand with Tanzania's determination to achieve a middle-income status by 2025 through an ambitious industrialization plan. The government has also taken steps to improve the business environment, including simplifying business registration procedures and reducing the time and cost required to start a business. Among these efforts is adoption of the online business registration policy as of 2018.

In addition to efforts in improving business registration, the country is also determined that the growth is science, technology and innovation (STI) led. One of the efforts towards this direction is to improve the amount of resources committed to research and development (R&D). In 2022, Tanzania's gross domestic expenditure on R&D (GERD) equaled 0.52 percent of its GDP where 42% of this financing comes from external sources (Fosci et al, 2019). While this is much more compared to the average GERD for low income countries, an overreliance on external funding can be problematic in terms of sustainability of the efforts.

Looking at the information and communication technologies (ICT) infrastructure, Tanzania has been rapidly improving in recent years, with significant investment in broadband internet connectivity and mobile phone networks. According to the 2020 report by the Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA), the country has internet penetration rate of 49% with 28 million internet users⁵. The penetration of mobile services has also improved financial inclusion through the use of mobile money which in turn helps start-ups in their transaction. With this, the number of new businesses being created in Tanzania has been steadily increasing over the past few years, with a particular focus on the tech sector. According to a 2017 study by the World Bank Tanzania has experienced a significant increase in the number of start-ups since 2009, with a growth rate of 33% (WB, 2017). This positive trend

²<https://www.nbs.go.tz/index.php/en/>

³<https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/field/population/country-comparison>

⁴<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.UEM.TOTL.ZS?locations=TZ>

⁵https://www.tcra.go.tz/uploads/text-editor/files/TelCom%20Statistics%20March%202021_1621231788.pdf

notwithstanding however, Tanzanian startups are failing at an alarming rate! In fact, nearly 70% of startups fail within the first three years⁶.

In terms of sectoral focus, major areas for startups are, **agriculture and agribusiness**: Startups focusing on improving agricultural practices, market access for farmers, and agri-tech solutions, and **Fintech**: Mobile payment solutions, digital banking, and financial inclusion initiatives were gaining traction.

Socially, Tanzania has a diverse population with over 120 ethnic groups, each with its unique language and culture. However, Kiswahili is a common language spoken by each of these diverse groups with English being the second official language next to Kiswahili. The country's life expectancy is around 66 years according to the World Health Organization (WHO) and has made significant progress in reducing poverty, with the poverty rate declining from over 60% in 2007 to around 25% in 2019. However due to the COVID-19 pandemic effects, the poverty rate again increased to 27% in 2021⁷

Tanzania has also made strides in improving access to education, with primary school enrolment rates reaching nearly 100% in recent years. However, quality and access to secondary and tertiary education are still limited. The poor quality education is also reflected in employment rates: while about 800,000 youth in Tanzania enter the job market annually, only about 40,000 formal jobs are available⁸.

4.1.2 Status of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems of Tanzania

Finance

Tanzania's innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystem is still emerging and growing. While there are several initiatives and programs aimed at promoting innovation and entrepreneurship, the country is still facing significant challenges in accessing finance for startups and small businesses. In particular, the entrepreneurship ecosystem in Tanzania is still facing challenges to attract external funding. One of the critical gaps is the lack of angel investment activities and venture capitalists within the local ecosystem, as well as the existence of competitive grant processes that support a variety of start-ups to continue developing their ventures (International Trade Center and COSTECH, ND). This has been confirmed by the focus group discussion and individuals that were interviewed; that most entrepreneurs start their business by using their own savings and those from family and friends; that it is not easy to secure a loan from any financial institution for a new business. Reasons for this – in addition to limited sources of finance - include high collateral requirements by the banks, low levels of financial literacy, and weak legal and regulatory frameworks.

⁶ https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/10-true-ales-how-tanzanian-startups-fail-isai-mathias?trk=pulse-article_more-articles_related-content-card

⁷ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/tanzania/overview>

⁸ <https://www.technoserve.org/blog/youth-unemployment-entrepreneurship/>

Lack of finance for startups especially affects technology based and growth oriented startups such as renewable energy and ICT related ventures. For renewable energy for instance, due to the significant initial expenses and the greater uncertainty associated with bringing renewable energy projects to market as compared to traditional technologies, there is a hindrance to obtaining funding for renewable energy initiatives (Lam et al, 2016; Sergi et al 2018). Although the national commission for science and technology provide funding for such startups, but this is at very small scale compared to the business ideas that are out there.

Culture

According to what is documented in literature, Tanzania appears to have a vibrant entrepreneurship culture, with a growing sense of opportunity and optimism. However, this could have been facilitated more by scarcity of job opportunities rather than purely entrepreneurial drive. This fact has been substantiated by both the focus group discussion (FGD) and individual interviews that were carried out, where the majority of the participants indicated they have been pushed to start businesses as a survival strategy because they could not find employment elsewhere in the country.

Given the above situation, there are programs initiated to instill the entrepreneurship culture in the country, including courses on entrepreneurship in higher learning institutions. The university (e.g. University of Dar Es Salaam) has also started a short term entrepreneurship programs to those who graduated from this university, but also including everybody else that is interested. The program is aimed at developing an entrepreneurial mindset in students as well as motivating them to start their own businesses (Alliance for African Partnership, 2022)

Human capital

One of the main challenges of the Tanzanian entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystems is limited access to quality education and training. Many young people in Tanzania lack access to basic education, and those who did attend school often receive a low-quality education that fails to equip them with the skills and knowledge they need to succeed either as employees of other organizations or as entrepreneurs. While there are some initiatives aimed at promoting STEM education and various skills development programs, there still exists a huge skill gap in various areas of employment, which calls for further government intervention to improve educational outcomes.⁹ Much of this is related to the quality of education. According to Human Capital Index 2020, if a Tanzanian child complete education and has full health, has only 39 percent of being productive when she/he grows up¹⁰, which is slightly lower than the average for Sub-Saharan Africa countries. This means, while Tanzania has a large and growing population, the education and skills of the workforce are often inadequate to meet the needs of a rapidly evolving economy. To address the challenge, the country is implementing a number of programs to address the problem. Specifically for entrepreneurship, the National Economic

⁹<https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/tanzania/publication/tanzania-economic-update-investing-in-human-capital>

¹⁰https://databankfiles.worldbank.org/public/ddpext_download/hci/HCI_2pager_TZA.pdf

Empowerment Council created a plan in 2017 to optimize a regulatory framework, enhance entrepreneurship education and skill development, facilitate technology exchange and innovation, improve access to finance, and promote awareness and networking within the country. Universities in Tanzania have also been offering training in entrepreneurship for all its degree programs. This notwithstanding, the program faces a number of challenges, the two on top being inadequate number of trainers – given the huge number of students, and only theoretically based training with very little facilities to facilitate hands-on training and learning (Alliance for African Partnership, 2022).

However, despite these overall challenges, there are some isolated best practices based at the university. One is a program that attempts to motivate and develop youth champions who can create their own employment opportunities, is the University of Dar es Salaam's Annual Innovation and Entrepreneurship Challenge (UD-AIEC) initiated in 2019. Through this program students benefit not only from the monetary prizes but also entrepreneurship awareness seminars, pitching skills training, networking, and for the winners being incubated to continue working on their innovative business ideas in the UDSM incubator which is hosted under UDIEC.

Additionally, there are also some emerging private sector initiatives aimed at promoting skills development and innovation. For example, several technology hubs and incubators – apart from providing services to start-ups - have launched platforms for young people to develop their skills and connect them with potential employers.

Access to Markets

Access to markets in Tanzania remains a challenge for many businesses, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and startups. While Tanzania has a large and growing population of about 62 million, many businesses struggled to access markets beyond their local communities. Some of the challenges include limited platforms and resources for businesses to connect with potential customers or partners. This makes it difficult for businesses to identify and reach new markets, particularly those outside of their immediate geographic area. The focus group discussion indicated that market access- both local and export are very challenging – especially if it is a new product. For the local market, one has to spend a lot of money in product promotion; and that many young entrepreneurs do not have such a large amount of resources. On the other hand, the participants of the focus group discussion also argued that for the export market there are additional huddles: there are a number of requirements that one needs to understand, and a number of authorities to seek permits from, as a result the process becomes tedious and costly.

However, the government of Tanzania is trying to address some of the above huddles. For example, the government launched several initiatives aimed at promoting trade and investment, such as the Tanzania Trade Development Authority (TanTrade)¹¹, which provides support and resources to businesses looking to expand their markets. There are also other agencies like the

¹¹<https://www.tantrade.go.tz/>

Tanzania Investment Centre (TIC)¹² whose mission is to coordinate, promote and facilitate investments in Tanzania and advise the Government on policy matters in order to create a competitive, attractive and sustainable investment climate.

Additionally, there are some emerging digital platforms and e-commerce initiatives that have the potential to connect businesses with new markets. For example, Jumia, a leading e-commerce platform in Africa, had launched operations in Tanzania, providing a new channel for businesses to sell their products to customers across the country. Overall, we can say that while access to markets remains a challenge in Tanzania, there are also positive developments that suggest potential for growth and expansion in the future.

Support systems and interactive linkage

In addition to the physical infrastructure – which as described in the section on social and economic context – is not bad, there are knowledge related infrastructure, which include Research and development institutions, Higher learning institutions, incubators and accelerators, Angel investors, Venture capitalists, local corporations, governments and startups themselves.

In regard to the above, we discuss two things: adequacy and interactive linkage among themselves. Regarding adequacy and strength of linkage among the entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem actors in Tanzania, the picture we got from literature and discussion with some of the system actors, indicate that some of the system actors such as angel investors and venture capitalists, large corporations are in short supply in Tanzania. As explained by some of the interviews, the problem with the venture capital is actually not that of inadequacy, but demand for these actors. They explained that venture capitalists actually came to the market, but left because they could not find start-ups that are venture capital ready.

On the other hand, it appears – especially for the two sectors under investigation – there are adequate number of incubators and accelerators, and most of the existing startups are somehow well connected to these. For instance, the report by the International Business Center and COSTECH indicate that about 75% of the startups in ICT related ventures are connected to incubators and accelerators. While this would have been a very good thing as most incubators and accelerators are put in place to provide support to entrepreneurs in host of business services, unfortunately this is not the case: According to the existing literature (see for instance International Trade Center and COSTESCH, ND), most of the incubators and accelerators provides support only in the ideation stage and prototyping, with very little on the much needed middle stage support of testing the idea in the market (proof of concept), and third stage of growing the business and to scale. This challenge is also supported by the focus group discussion (FGD), where entrepreneurs complained that hubs and innovation spaces are offering the same kind of services; mostly on ideation, and very little on latter stages of market testing of the product, acceleration and scaling. Interviews with some of the hubs management however indicated that this is because most entrepreneurs do not understand at what stages their

¹²<https://www.tic.go.tz/pages/access-to-markets>

businesses are; they say some entrepreneurs may come and want to be accelerated, but in actual fact they are still in the ideation stage, so we have to give that first.

In addition, discussion with the two hubs officials indicated that, problem related to lack of the overall coordinator of the hubs compounds the above problems. This is supported by earlier studies, where the literature indicates that the ecosystem lacks structure to track hubs' activities, to understand what programme exists in the ecosystem and how each hub can align systematically to complement each other, rather than duplicating efforts. Resulting into ecosystem actors, including funders, to miss the holistic view of the ecosystem to avoid overlaps and ensure there is sufficient support in each stage of entrepreneurship development (International Trade Center and COSTECH, ND).

Another problem for Tanzanian technology based start-ups is lack of strong connections with the R&D and training institutions that are a source of knowledge and ideas for starting and growing businesses. These organizations are not in short supply in Tanzania, but the challenge is their connection with entrepreneurs. In addition, while connection among entrepreneurs and startups is extremely important to learn from each, connections between individual startups are extremely rare in Tanzania. According to the International Business Center and COSTECH report, only 7% of those businesses they interviewed have connections with each other. On the other hand, connection with policy makers seems to be sporadic and many of the interviewed entrepreneurs are not aware of the existence of the policies that potentially supports them – although currently with the initiation of the Tanzania Start-ups Association, there is an ongoing and regular government debate with start-ups through this organization.

Policy and business environment

Despite Tanzania having in place a number of policies, including the Sustainable Industries Development Policy (SIDP) (1996)¹³, which among other - aims to create an enabling environment for entrepreneurship. However, in practice this is not always the case. For instance, there is not only no support for innovation in the case of technology based startups, but also road blocks. According to the recent study by Diyamett&Mwighusa (2023), Fintech startups are not allowed to market new digital financial services products, unless the product has worked elsewhere in the world – the practice that is against innovation practices, especially those that are new to the world. More generally -according to focus group discussion - despite the existence of different kind of support policies, the general business environment in Tanzania is not friendly. Summarizing the views of most participants, “bureaucracy is one of the major challenges to do a business in Tanzania. The processing of registering business involves a number of documentations of which information is not readily available. This leads to the delay in obtaining various permits, and at times the time it will take to get all the necessary permits is unpredictable. These complaints were expressed by both local and foreign investors. Foreign investors have explained that although the government offers opportunities for foreign investment, there is no easy way, most of the incentives provided are largely only in blue prints,

¹³https://www.mit.go.tz/uploads/files/SIDP_Policy222.pdf

with little implementation. The interview with one of the foreign entrepreneurs in renewable energy indicates that it is generally not easy to locate business in Tanzania. There is no proper commitment. The entrepreneur further urged that one can establish a business and then 10 years later the Tanzania Electric Supply Company (TANESCO) or the Rural Electrification Authority (REA) reaches the place to supply electricity there. In such conditions, you are obliged to remove your infrastructure. So, this requires you to think twice before establishing a plant somewhere in Tanzania. In addition, foreign investors argue that there is no binding legal framework that forces REA or TANESCO to buy your established infrastructure even though we use TANESCO grid code. On a more positive side, they thank the partnership with SAUT to facilitate their establishment since the investment process was not so straightforward to understand what and when each step takes in the investment process. Other Challenges include weaknesses to deal with counterfeit products (e.g. solar batteries – for renewable energy) in the market, which affect not only foreign businesses, but also local investments.

In addition, the group discussion expressed dissatisfaction with the existence of multiple regulators within a particular business, a challenge which also results in multiple taxations. e.g., a telecom company has to pay taxes to TCRA, The Universal Communications Service Access Fund (UCSAF) and Bank of Tanzania (BOT) at the same time for one product that a firm is offering.

Generally, the group discussion indicated that ease in starting a business in Tanzania really depends on the type of business. According to the discussion, it is relatively easier to start a business in low tech, service-oriented sectors and much more difficult for technology-based businesses due to the need for specialized skills and equipment. This can be explained by the fact that the Tanzanian economy is still a low tech economy, and therefore infrastructure and skills are not readily available for such sectors.

4.1.3 Summary and concluding remarks

Human resources: There is a capacity problem - many of the entrepreneurs who start business do not have expertise in business management and leadership, and cannot find skilled employees to run a successful business – given the theory based learning in school. While elsewhere incubators and accelerators elsewhere have helped in such capacity building and business mentorship, according to the entrepreneurs we spoke to, most managers of these structures and their facilitators are not entrepreneurs, and therefore they themselves do not have practical experience in advising or training start-ups.

Culture and entrepreneurial mind set: Tanzania is a large country with a good size of population, which is largely youthful - most of who are without formal employment. While this is a huge opportunity for entrepreneurship, many of these young people start business out of mere need to survive, rather than entrepreneurial drive. University in Tanzania provides entrepreneurship training to instill entrepreneurial mind set; but such training has not been useful because it is largely theory based, with very little, if at all, hands-on experiential learning.

Finance: Inadequate finance for the growth of the Tanzanian entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem is very well documented in literature. In addition, all the stakeholders we spoke to highlighted this as one of the major problems facing the Tanzanian ecosystem. There are two

major type of finance that Tanzanian ecosystem seem to desperately need: adequate finance for the hubs (incubators and accelerators) to provide appropriate and adequate service to entrepreneurs); second is finance for the second stage of market trials or proof of concept on the part of the entrepreneurs, normally provided by the angel investors, because without such finance, it is very difficult for an entrepreneur – however good he/she may be, to succeed.

Access to markets: The problem of access to markets by the entrepreneurs in Tanzania is well documented in literature, and is also one of the major complaints of those we spoke to. This is a very unfortunate situation because Tanzania is a large country with a large and increasing population. Perhaps startups need to do market research and be innovative in marketing, but again this is part of the skills that they lack.

Weak interactive linkage among ecosystem actors: linkage among the entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems actors is what makes an entrepreneur succeed. Unfortunately, for the Tanzanian market, there are two challenges: first is inadequacy of the actors, and second is lack of linkage among themselves – this is especially the case for the linkage between incubators and start-ups, and R&D and higher learning institutions, leading to low investments in knowledge based ventures that are important for growth and employment generation.

4.2 South Africa

4.2.1 Social and economic context

South Africa – a country with a size of 1.22 million square kilometers and population of 60.2 million people (according to World Bank, as of 2021) - is considered to be the most developed economy in the African continent, which makes it an attractive market for businesses looking to expand their operations outside of Europe. The country has a high mobile connectivity and internet penetration: over 90% of the population is covered by at least a 3G mobile network, and internet penetration is above the world average of 51%. More than 85% of South African households are reportedly connected to the national electricity grid. South Africa also invests in science, technology and innovation more than any other African country. For instance gross expenditure on R&D (GERD) as a share of GDP in South Africa¹⁴ is the highest in the SADC¹⁵ region: 0.83%, with sources of funds coming mostly from the state (46.7%), businesses (41.5%) and from abroad (10.5%), according to the UNESCO Institute of Statistics.

In terms of start-ups, The South Africa ecosystem is one of the most robust and developed on the continent – thanks to several strengths, including significant consumer and business markets, sophisticated entrepreneurial talent, and strong corporate sector. In terms of numbers, at least 490 tech startups were in operation across South Africa as of May 2022, employing over 11,000 people between them. Fintech is the most populated sector, with almost one-third of the country’s tech startups active in that vertical (Disrupt Africa, 2022). In terms of survival, South African startups are by far the most successful when it comes to successful exits. Since 2015, 35 South African tech startups have been acquired, accounting for one-third of the acquisitions tracked by Disrupt Africa across the entire continent in the last 7.5 years

In terms of social and economic indicators the country has a GDP of US\$419 billion in 2021 (according to International Monetary Fund), and GDP per capita of US\$5.450 (according to World Bank, as of 2021). In line with these important economic indicators the country has a Life expectancy of 63 years (according to World Health Organisation, as of 2021). However, along with this somehow impressive economic statistics, the country has unemployment Status of 55% in 2019”, which is the highest in the SADC region (Keamer-Mbule et al. 2021, p. 562). This to a large extent is because South Africa “remains a dual economy with one of the highest and most persistent inequality rates in the world. This duality has been maintained by limited advances in social inclusion and the incapacity to create sufficient jobs. The great natural resources of the country can be added to the list of opportunities for businesses. South Africa is rich in natural resources such as gold, platinum and diamonds. This presents great chances for businesses in the mining and resource sectors. South Africa, and especially Cape Town, also has a well- developed infrastructure, including a network of roads, ports and airports. This

¹⁴Gross domestic expenditure on R&D (GERD) as a percentage of GDP is the total intramural expenditure on R&D performed in the national territory during a specific reference period expressed as a percentage of GDP of the national territory (Source: UNESCO Institute of Statistics)

¹⁵Southern Africa Development Community

makes it easy for businesses to transport their goods and services within the city and across the country. The market for investment in Cape Town – which is the most vibrant city when it comes to startups - continues to look increasingly promising, both for local investors and international ones. Cape Town has a vibrant and diverse economy, with a range of opportunities for investment across different sectors. The city has a large and growing technology sector, with companies like Amazon and Microsoft establishing a presence in the area. Other key industries in the city include tourism, manufacturing and agriculture. But generally major sectors for startups are **Fintech**: South Africa has a well-established fintech sector, including digital payment solutions and peer-to-peer lending platforms, and **E-commerce**: Growth in online retail and related services

4.2.2 Status of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems of South Africa

Finance

According to existing literature more generally finance for startups in South Africa is not a big problem. According to Disrupt Africa (2022) for instance, South Africa has access to local capital and ties to a growing number of international investors. The report also indicates these startups are also supported by a strong investment ecosystem - at least 357 individual South African tech startups raised a combined US\$993,684,600 in funding between January 2015 and May 2022, a figure topped only by Nigeria over that time. The report further states funding, both in terms of the number of startups backed and the total tally secured, has generally increased over years, most especially in the last three years. For small to medium-sized businesses in South Africa, bank loans are the most common source of finance. The South African government offers a range of grants and funding schemes to support these businesses as well. These include the Small Enterprise Finance Agency (SEFA), who provide development finances to SMMEs and cooperatives who are unable to attract commercial credit, and the Industrial Development Corporation (IDC), which was established in 1940 through the Industrial Development Corporation Act and is supporting industrial capacity development and funding high-impact projects¹⁶. A growing trend, noticeable in Cape Town, when it comes to investing and financing is Philanthropic Capital. More investors seem to fund businesses that create a positive and environmental impact¹⁷

The above notwithstanding, close look – like the interviews carried out by the ENRICH in Africa project – indicate all is not that well as far as financing of startups is concerned. Most of those interviewed – both as individuals and in focus group discussions, see the access to capital in the early stage as a remaining problem for most entrepreneurs who are trying to bring new and innovative ideas to market; that late stage entrepreneurs get more attention and access to capital, whereas pre-seed and early stage entrepreneurs are left with next to nothing.

¹⁶ Investment promotion – The Department of Trade Industry and Competition (thedtic.gov.za)

¹⁷ Impact - Bertha Foundation

Culture

In terms of entrepreneurship culture, South Africa – especially its major cities – is rich. For the Cape Town, which is the focus of the study, one of the key drivers of this culture is the presence of a number of successful tech companies that have been founded in the city, such as GetSmarter, Yoco and Zoono. Cape Town’s universities have also played a significant role in fostering an entrepreneurial culture, giving young and promising potential entrepreneurs the chance to follow their dreams. The University of Cape Town (UCT), for example, has a dedicated entrepreneurship centre that offers mentorship, funding and networking opportunities for students and alumni who are interested in starting their own businesses

Human capital

South Africa has a well-established education system with many universities and technical and vocational education and training (TVET) colleges across the country. The universities offer a wide range of undergraduate and postgraduate programs, including business, engineering, science and law. SA has recognized the importance of entrepreneurship and innovation in developing human capital and promoting economic growth. Several universities in the country offer specific entrepreneurship and innovation education, for example: The University of Cape Town’s Graduate School of Business offers a Master in Entrepreneurship and New Venture Creation¹⁸. The program aims to develop graduates who are equipped with the skills and knowledge to create and grow successful businesses. Others are: Pretoria’s Gordon Institute of Business Science (GIBS) which offers an Entrepreneurship Development Programme that provide participants with the skills and knowledge to start their own businesses and the University of the Witwatersrand’s Tshimologong Digital Innovation Precinct offers an incubation program for tech start-ups, providing mentoring, training and access to resources¹⁹

Access to markets

While entrepreneurship seems to be thriving in South Africa, especially in cities such as Cape Town, and that markets are far better than elsewhere in Africa, there are still challenges, especially around markets for the products. According to individual interviews and focus group discussion, South Africa’s location poses a challenge in itself and that entrepreneurs face difficulties when trying to bring new and innovative ideas to the market. They point out lack of access to a sizable market due to inadequate local market (given the size of entrepreneurial ventures), and the neighboring ones being so different – making it difficult to grow and expand. Additionally, access to export markets is a major challenge; most of the South African tech startups, even those existing for many years and being post Series A and Series B, are still only based in South Africa and they struggle with moving overseas and operating in multiple countries.

¹⁸ 15 What we do | Cape Chamber of Commerce & Industry

¹⁹ Entrepreneurship Development Academy | Centres | About Us | GIBS

Support system and interactive linkage

Physical infrastructure

In terms of physical infrastructure – one of these being telecommunications - Cape Town has a well-developed telecommunications infrastructure that includes fibre-optic and wireless networks, enabling businesses to access high-speed internet connectivity. When it comes to transportation, Cape Town is at the forefront of easy transportation in reference to the African continent. Its transportation infrastructure includes a network of highways, railways and air transportation.

Support actors – knowledge and finance infrastructure

Business services

There is a number of business services in SA business ecosystem environment that can be utilized by the startups. These include Chamber of Commerce and Industry, a non-profit organization that promotes and protects the interests of businesses. The organization offers business training and network opportunities, amongst other services. It also assists foreign entrepreneurs with setting up their businesses in major cities, e.gCape Town. It has a dedicated team that provides guidance and advice on the legal and regulatory requirements for establishing a business in South Africa²⁰. Cape Town also hosts a number of startup events annually such as the African Tech Summit and Cape Town Startup Week, which provide opportunities for networking, mentorship and exposure to potential investors.

Venture capital

There is a growing venture capital in South Africa, especially in major cities such as Cape Town. Some of the notable venture capitalists in Cape Town include, Launch Africa Ventures, HAVAiC, Kalon Venture Partners and AngelHub Venture. South Africa is one of only four countries that receive around 85% of the Africa's total venture capital investments, as well as 70% of STEM graduates (Maher et al.2021).

Innovation hubs and centers

South Africa has at least 93 Active technology hubs. This makes it the second country in Africa in terms of the number of technology hubs (after Nigeria: 101). This is also significant given the total number of tech hubs in Africa: 744. Tech hubs usually cover areas that range from fintech, health, education, agriculture, big data and analytics, software, cleantech, and digital economy (Kraemer-Mbula et al. 2021).

²⁰ What we do | Cape Chamber of Commerce & Industry

Universities and research centers

South African Big Cities, such as Cape Town house a good number of universities and research centers that are potentially power house for ideas for innovation and startups. South Africa actually has one of the, if not the most, developed academic research firepower and there are amazing things happening in South Africa, especially at the universities. However, according to those interviewed by the project, there is very poor technological support for the young entrepreneurs and innovation spaces are very inactive as a result. The interviewed proposed there should be a connection between investments being made in science and the entrepreneurial activities.

Government policies

The South African government has implemented various initiatives to support and encourage the growth of small businesses and medium-sized enterprises. The government also continues to implement various policies to attract foreign investment and increase economic growth. The Department of Trade, Industry and Competition (DTIC) is the main government body responsible to effectuate these policies. Some of these policies include tax incentives for foreign investors, such as tax breaks on capital investments, research and development, and training²¹. This notwithstanding, however, according to the interviews carried out by the project, founders generally face regulatory huddles when trying to bring new and innovative ideas to market: Although there is a startup Act inplace, according to the interviewees there is a lot of work to be done in order to get a Startup Act across the line.

4.2.3 Summary and concluding remarks

South Africa – a country with a size of 1.22 million square kilometers and population of 60.2 million people (according to World Bank, as of 2021) - is considered to be the most developed economy in the African continent, which makes it an attractive market for businesses looking to expand their operations outside of Europe. In terms of technology, South Africa is also one of the highly developed countries in Africa. The country has a high mobile connectivity and internet penetration: over 90% of the population is covered by at least a 3G mobile network, and internet penetration is above the world average of 51%. The country invests in science, technology and innovation more than any other African country. For instance gross expenditure on R&D (GERD) as a share of GDP in South Africa is the highest in the SADC region: 0.83%, with sources of funds coming mostly from the state (46.7%), businesses (41.5%) and from abroad (10.5%). What also stands out from other African countries is contribution of the country's private sector to R&D – many of the African countries' private sector contribute only a meagre resources, if at all.

In line with the above, South Africa is far ahead of many of the African when it comes to entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem development – although of course some major challenges remain as follows:

²¹ South African Tax and investment incentive – South African Tax Guide (sataxguide.co.za)

Finance: As against many African countries, South Africa has access to local capital and ties to a growing number of international investors. This notwithstanding, however, this capital seems to be available, to a large extent, to the more mature startups, with those on early stage who are trying to bring new and innovative ideas to market, access to capital is still a major problem.

Human capital: South Africa has a well-established education system with many universities and technical and vocational education and training (TVET) colleges across the country, which offers a wide range of undergraduate and postgraduate programs, including business, engineering, science and law. The country has recognized the importance of entrepreneurship and innovation in promoting economic growth. Several universities in the country offer specific entrepreneurship and innovation education. But still there seem to be a disconnect between the science and entrepreneurial activities; there is also a problem of brain drain.

Access to markets:

While entrepreneurship seems to be thriving in South Africa, especially in cities such as Cape Town, there are challenges around markets for the products. According to individual interviews and focus group discussion, South Africa's location poses a challenge in itself and that entrepreneurs face difficulties when trying to bring new and innovative ideas to the market. They point out lack of access to a sizable market due to the local market being inadequate – in line with the thriving entrepreneurship, and that the neighboring ones being are different, making it difficult for businesses to grow and expand. In addition, access to international markets seems to be problematic.

Linkage among system actors: South Africa seems to be very rich when it comes to entrepreneurship and innovation system actors. For one, the country has a high number of technology hubs- it is second in the whole of Africa; first being Nigeria. The country also house a good number of universities and research centers that are potentially power house for ideas for innovation and startups. This notwithstanding however, there is very poor connection between these hubs and the academia.

Government policies and business environment: Although the South African government has implemented various initiatives to support and encourage the growth of small businesses and medium-sized enterprises, including the Startup Act, according to those interviewed, founders generally face regulatory and financial huddles when trying to bring new and innovative ideas to market; and the existing Startup Act seems not helpful because of inadequate implementation.

4.3 Ghana

4.3.1 Social and economic context

Ghana, located in West Africa – with a population of approximately 33 million people as of 2022 – is a thriving nation with a stable democracy. It is considered one of Africa's fastest-growing economies, with a mix of agriculture, industry, and services all contributing to its growth. During pre-pandemic, the country had a growth rate of 6.5% in 2019, according to the IMF²². Nonetheless the country's economy heavily depends on export earnings from just a few commodities, such as gold, oil, and cocoa, and as a result the fluctuating world market prices for these commodities considerably impact the country's economic situation.

Regarding the social context, Ghana – like many other African countries – has a youthful population; over 60% are under 25. The literacy rate in Ghana is now at 69.8 percent: a report of the 2021 Population and Housing Census conducted by the Ghana Statistical Service has indicated. The country has lower adult literacy levels than its comparators (lower middle-income and sub-Saharan African countries). And poverty and income inequality remain significant challenges, with nearly a quarter of the population living below the poverty line. About 1.76 million persons were unemployed in the third quarter of 2022.

Regarding state of entrepreneurship and business startups, Ghana has a relatively high rate of early-stage entrepreneurial activity compared to many Sub-Saharan African countries. Two major sectors are prominent for startups: **Fintech, which** is a leading sector for startups in Ghana, with a focus on innovative solutions for mobile payments, digital banking, and financial inclusion. Startups in this sector aim to provide accessible and efficient financial services to a broader population; and **Agriculture and Agribusiness**: Given Ghana's strong agricultural base, startups in the agriculture and agribusiness sector are prominent. These startups work on solutions to improve agricultural productivity, supply chain efficiency, and market access for farmers, contributing to the development of the agricultural ecosystem

Several initiatives also aim to support start-ups and entrepreneurs, including incubators and accelerators, co-working spaces, and entrepreneurship training programs. Ghana has the second highest internet penetration in sub-Saharan Africa, at 53% in 2022, making it particularly appealing to tech companies.

The above impressive situation notwithstanding however, a significant number of start-ups fail. According to the Deputy Finance Minister, about 74% of start-ups fail in Ghana – just like in Tanzania.

4.3.2 Status of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems of Ghana

Finance

There are many sources of finance for starting a business in Ghana, including support from family and friends, incubators and accelerators, angel investor networks, foundations, banks, venture capital firms, public funders, and private equity firms – available at differing degrees,

²²FDI Intelligence, IMF: African economies are the world's fastest growing, 2019

with angel investors and venture capitalists the least, and banks the leading²³. Despite all these, entrepreneurs in Ghana still face significant challenges in accessing finance. The focus group discussion mentioned that there is a lack of local venture capitalists who understand the market, which will allow them to offer businesses funds at good rates and with flexible payment terms. On the other hand, although there is an appetite from venture capitalists to invest in Ghana, many have cited the lack of strong pipeline of investible companies as a reason for the limited volume of deals; and a significant proportion of Ghanaian businesses lack the strong cashflows, accounting structures and long-term business planning and marketing skills needed to attract investment²⁴. Another member of the focus group participants highlighted that there are many rich Ghanaians, but they prefer to use their funds to purchase houses and cars than to support locals who need business funds. In addition, Ghanaian entrepreneurs have traditionally been reluctant to give up equity in their businesses, which limits the set of options available for equity providers²⁵

Culture

In the face of inadequate employment, many Ghanaians have been forced to start small businesses as a source of income. So in actual fact, the culture of entrepreneurship is not there. This is irrespective of some parents being entrepreneurs. Parents prefer their children to have white-collar jobs as this seems to be a more prestigious career. According to the participants of a focus group discussion, there is no innovation in the entrepreneurship ecosystem in Ghana because many of the businesses are copy of concepts used in the Western world. In the words of the participants, it is like "cut, edit and paste." Also, the educational system in Ghana does not help much because it is theory-based, and therefore hinders the creativity and innovation of many Ghanaians. This notwithstanding however, many existing founders who have been able to succeed in entrepreneurship now offer support to many upcoming entrepreneurs in the form of mentorship. This includes foreigners as Ghanaians are generally welcoming of foreign ventures. There are many positive stories of foreign founders in Ghana, and this has encouraged many Diasporas to scale and even start new businesses in Ghana. With the upspring of accelerator programs and grants for entrepreneurs across Ghana – buttressed with flexible government policies and structures for foreign investors – the international perception of entrepreneurship in Ghana looks positive.

Human capital

The Ghanaian education system is divided into three parts: basic education, secondary education, and tertiary education, which are expected to be completed over 11 years. The literacy rate in Ghana as of 2020 is 80.38%. Despite the progress Ghana has made in improving

²³<https://ecosystems.andeglobal.org/ANDE%20Financial%20Constraints%20in%20Ghana%20Report.pdf>

²⁴<https://ecosystems.andeglobal.org/ANDE%20Financial%20Constraints%20in%20Ghana%20Report.pdf>

²⁵<https://ecosystems.andeglobal.org/ANDE%20Financial%20Constraints%20in%20Ghana%20Report.pdf>

access to education for all, there are still challenges preventing thousands of children from going to school and learning in rural areas. Moreover, for those who are lucky to attend school – even up to the tertiary level - there is an issue of unpreparedness of the graduates. This has been attributed to the theory-based nature of the Ghanaian education curriculums, which do not give students the practical skills to prepare them for the job market. And therefore recruiters have to spend extra time and resources training their staff or recruiting from other countries. There is also the issue of brain drain in Ghana, especially in the health sector. This can be attributed to the higher wages, better opportunities, and a higher standard of living elsewhere in the world – especially the Western rich countries.

Access to markets

There are a few networks in Ghana that provide support to foreign and diaspora entrepreneurs. Some of these networks include the American Chamber of Commerce – Ghana (AMCHAM) and Impact Hub Accra. They provide support through commercial introductions, country visits, and identification of local partners, which helps provide some soft landing for foreign and Diaspora in Ghana.

Support systems and interactive linkages

Physical infrastructure

In terms of infrastructure, Ghana has fairly good roads. And regarding connectivity, the country has excellent internet connectivity. The country has four registered mobile operators: MTN, Vodafone, Glo Ghana, and AirtelTigo, with MTN having the biggest market share. In terms of power, Ghana's power supply sources are from hydroelectricity, thermal fueled by crude oil, natural gas and diesel, solar, and imports from La Cote D'Ivoire. Ghana also exports power to Togo, Benin, and Burkina Faso. Ghana has made significant progress in increasing electricity generation and access. However, beneath these improvements lies inefficiencies, including extraordinarily high distribution losses. Electricity is also quite expensive in Ghana.

Knowledge infrastructure – actors

Ghana currently has over 200 non-financial actors providing a wide range of services to SGBs. Capacity development actors, including business development service (BDS) providers and specialized consultants, are the most prevalent type of organization. A 2020 survey of key actors in the ecosystem found that 41 percent of organizations surveyed identified as capacity development providers, and half of programs offered included technical assistance (TA) or capacity building. Incubators and co working spaces also represented a popular form of support for SGBs, with 20 percent of organizations offering the service. Other important non-financial actors in the ecosystem include incubators, accelerators, foundations, academic institutions, and research organizations (ANDE, 2021)

Government policies and business environment

There are clear policies and structures to start a business in Ghana. The country has implemented initiatives and policies to support both innovation and entrepreneurship, some of which include:

- The 2017 Tax Incentive/Tax Holidays for Young Entrepreneurs in Ghana. The government in 2017 adopted a tax policy that incentivizes small businesses by easing their tax burden. This time the policy was targeted at young people. Following promises made in the budget statement, the Income Tax Act 10 (Amendment No.2) 2017 Act 956 was passed to provide a special tax holiday for young entrepreneurs in selected business ventures.
- YouStart initiative, as captured in the 2022 Annual Budget, would support youth-led enterprises with soft loans of up to GH¢50,000 to help startups (by young graduates and school leavers) and small businesses to expand, Starter packs (Soft loans tied to equipment acquisition) of up to GH¢50,000 for startups. In November 2022 Government of Ghana opened the portal for receiving applications from potential beneficiaries of the GHC1 billion funded initiative and eligible applicants to register²⁶
- The National Entrepreneurship and Innovation Plan (NEIP) is a flagship policy initiative of the government of Ghana with the primary objective of providing integrated national support for startups and small businesses. NEIP primarily focuses on providing business development services, startup incubators, and funding for young businesses to enable them to grow and become successful.

However, despite these good policies, availability of funding for entrepreneurs in Ghana is still a major problem. In the most recent World Bank Enterprise Survey for Ghana, 72 percent of small and 52 percent of growing businesses in Ghana identified access to finance as a major constraint—well above the Sub Saharan Africa average of 38 percent and global average 26 percent²⁷. In addition, according to focus group discussion - despite the existence of these policy frameworks, generally, the business environment in Ghana is not friendly. Summarizing the views of most participants, "Bureaucracy is one of the major challenges to doing business in Ghana. The processing of business registration involves some documentation of which information is not readily available. This leads to delays in obtaining various permits, and sometimes the time it takes to get all the necessary permits is unpredictable. Both local and foreign entrepreneurs expressed these complaints. Foreign entrepreneurs have explained that although the government offers opportunities for foreign investment, there is no easy way; most of the incentives provided are largely only in blueprints, with little implementation. Generally, the group discussion indicated that starting a business depends on the business type.

²⁶<https://www.nya.gov.gh/youstart-finally-launched-portal-opened-application>

²⁷World Bank, Enterprise Survey, 2019. (The number includes micro enterprises as well)

4.3.3 Summary and concluding remarks

Ghana, located in West Africa – with a population of approximately 33 million people as of 2022 – and a lower middle income country, is a thriving nation with a stable democracy, and considered one of Africa's fastest-growing economies, with a mix of agriculture, industry, and services all contributing to its growth. The country has a youthful population with over 60% under 25 – a breeding ground for entrepreneurship; and indeed the country has a relatively high rate of early-stage entrepreneurial activity compared to other Sub-Saharan African countries. Two major sectors are prominent for startups: **Fintech, which** is a leading sector for startups in Ghana, with a focus on innovative solutions for mobile payments, digital banking, and financial inclusion. Startups in this sector aim to provide accessible and efficient financial services to a broader population; and **Agriculture and Agribusiness**. Following are major challenges of the Ghanaian entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem:

- i) **Finance:** There are many sources of finance for starting a business in Ghana, including support from family and friends, incubators and accelerators, angel investor networks, foundations, banks, venture capital firms, public funders, and private equity firms – available at differing degrees, with angel investors and venture capitalists the least, and banks the leading. This notwithstanding, however, startups in Ghana still face significant challenges in accessing finance. Especially, there is lack of local venture capitalists who understand the market, which will allow them to offer businesses funds at good rates and with flexible payment terms.
- ii) **Human capital:** Despite the fact that literacy rate in Ghana, is high, there is challenge of capacity when it comes to entrepreneurship and innovation; first because the culture of entrepreneurship is low in Ghana; second is problem of unpreparedness of the graduates, attributed to the theory-based nature of the Ghanaian education curriculums. Finally, there is problem of brain drain, especially in the health sector. This can be attributed to the higher wages, better opportunities, and a higher standard of living elsewhere in the world – especially the Western rich countries.
- iii) **Linkage among system actors:** Ghana currently has over 200 non-financial actors providing a wide range of services to SGBs, with over 41 percent of organizations dealing with capacity development providers. The system actors are also poorly linked, and therefore have little impact on the performance of the startups.
- iv) **Government policies and business environment:** There are clear policies and structures to start a business in Ghana. The country has implemented a number of initiatives and policies to support both innovation and entrepreneurship. However, despite these good policies, availability of funding for entrepreneurs in Ghana is still a major problem, and business environment is not good enough – with bureaucracy a major challenge.

4.4 Zimbabwe

4.4.1 Social and economic context

Zimbabwe is a landlocked country located in southern Africa (See Figure 1 below), bordered by Zambia to the north, Mozambique to the east, South Africa to the south, and Botswana to the west, forming a large regional market of 125 million people. The Zimbabwean economy is heavily reliant on agriculture, mining, and tourism. The country is rich in natural resources, including gold, platinum, diamonds, and coal. The agricultural sector is dominated by small-scale farmers who produce crops such as maize, tobacco, and cotton. The tourism industry, with the country's national parks and game reserves attracts visitors from around the world. However, despite its natural resources and educated workforce, Zimbabwe has faced significant economic challenges since the early 2000s, due in part to a combination of political instability promoted by the Fast Track Land Reform Programme, corruption, and economic mismanagement which has affected its innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem. About 5 million Zimbabweans, including a substantial number of the country's professionals have, as a result, left the country to find work and economic opportunities in neighbouring countries such as Botswana and South Africa, as well as further abroad.

Zimbabwe has a population of approximately 15.1 million people, with the majority (61.4%²⁸) living in rural areas. The country has a literacy rate of 89.7%, which is one of the highest in Africa. With a 2023 Gross Domestic Product 2023 estimate of \$29.9 billion²⁹ by the International Monetary Fund, around US \$1851 per capita, the country is classified as a lower middle income country³⁰. Inflation has been a persistent problem, with rates reaching as high as 500 billion percent in 2008. Although the economy stabilised in 2009, with the introduction of the multi-currency system, inflation during peak-COVID year rose to 622% and continues to burden the business environment with rates of over 100% in 2022³¹. Due to the decline in commercial farming and exodus of multinational companies after the Fast Track Land Reform Programme, Zimbabwe's unemployment rate rose to unprecedented levels reaching 90% in 2012 according to the secretary-general of the Zimbabwe Congress of Trade Unions, Japhet Moyo. In 2008, the Indigenisation and Economic Empowerment Bill, signed into law by then President Robert Mugabe, required 51% ownership of all businesses to be transferred to locals disadvantaged by Zimbabwe's colonial history.

²⁸As reported in the National Financial Inclusion Strategy II Report

²⁹["World Economic Outlook Database, April 2023". IMF.org. International Monetary Fund.](#) April 2023. Retrieved 24 April 2023.

³⁰ African Development Bank: "African Economic Outlook 2021 From Debt resolution to Growth: The Road Ahead for Africa", AFDB, 2021, p. 39.,

³¹ <https://newswire.live/diaspora-by-the-numbers-zimbabweans-abroad-are-sending-home-9-times-more-money-than-fdi/#:~:text=Zimbabweans%20abroad%20sent%20home%20US,amounted%20to%20US%242.80%20billion>

However, while the indigenization legislation was politically polarizing, it contributed to the rise of local entrepreneurship and the participation of youth in business endeavours. When the current President, E.D Mnangagwa came to power in November 2017, the Indigenisation Laws were relaxed in order to attract foreign investment and transition the country to fully re-engage with the international community. The country has made progress in recent years and there are signs of a growing innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem. Zimbabwe remains an attractive destination for foreign investors due to its abundant natural resources, strategic location, and educated workforce. One of the key drivers of the innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem in Zimbabwe is the government's efforts to promote entrepreneurship. The government has also implemented various policies and programs to support entrepreneurship such as establishing innovation hubs in tertiary institutions and collaborating with development organisations on youth economic and empowerment programs. These initiatives provide funding and training for aspiring entrepreneurs, particularly for young people and women³². Major sectors for startups include **Fintech**: Given economic challenges, there was a focus on financial inclusion and digital payment systems; **Agriculture**: Startups addressing challenges in the agricultural value chain, and **E-commerce**: Similar to other African countries, e-commerce was on the rise.

4.4.2 Status of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems of Zimbabwe

Finance

Although a number of financial sources (including, debt financing, private equity, grants, Export credit facilities) are available in Zimbabwe, most start-ups in the country struggle to secure funding. Start-ups in Zimbabwe raised just US\$185 million over the past three years and most rely on personal finances, remittances (which make up 16% of the country's GDP) as well as grant funding. The government has introduced a number of initiatives aimed at increasing access to finance for SMEs, including the creation of a SME financing facility and the establishment of a credit guarantee scheme.

Access to finance is also challenging for the foreign investments, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) or brownfield investments³³ unless they partner with a local entity.

Culture

According to focus group discussions and individual interviews carried out by the project, the culture of entrepreneurship is very high in Zimbabwe - there are many individuals starting their own businesses in order to create employment and generate income; the youth no longer want to simply be accountants, lawyers or doctors but rather the next Elon Musk or Mark Zuckerberg.

³² <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/zimbabwe/overview#3>

³³When a company or government entity purchases or leases existing production facilities to launch a new production activity

The only deterrence for further mushrooming of this culture seems to be access to capital. Support from the government and private sector is also limited due to their focus on stabilizing the economy, dealing with issues such as a shortage of foreign currency, high inflation, and limited access to credit.

The entrepreneurship culture seems to be much stronger for women than men: Two of the male CEOs interviewed stated that they'd rather work with female entrepreneurs because they have more drive & entrepreneurship to prove and are more organised than their male counterparts.

Business culture in Zimbabwe is generally formal, with a strong emphasis on hierarchy and respect for authority. Building strong relationships with local partners and stakeholders is key to success in Zimbabwe and understanding the local culture and customs is important to building trust and credibility. It is therefore important for foreign investors to take the time to understand the local culture and customs in order to build strong relationships with local partners and stakeholders.

Human capital

Zimbabwe has a relatively well-educated workforce, with a literacy rate of 89.7%³⁴. However, the country has experienced significant brain drain since 2000, with many skilled professionals leaving to seek better opportunities abroad. This has led to a shortage of skilled workers in certain sectors, particularly in healthcare and education. The participants noted that entrepreneurship education needs to start in primary school because currently graduates are being thrust into entrepreneurship due to the high unemployment rates. The ratio of necessity entrepreneurs versus opportunity entrepreneurs is high. While Education 5.0³⁵ aims to address the dearth in technical & transferable skills, retaining talent is still difficult because remuneration & benefits levels are lower than in neighboring countries & further abroad. Oftentimes skilled employees use start-ups as the springboard to their migration ambitions.

Access to markets

According to those interviewed, access to markets is not a challenge to Zimbabwean entrepreneurs, as the country is part of the Southern African Development Community (SADC), a regional economic bloc that promotes trade and investment among member states. As a member of SADC, Zimbabwe has access to a market of over 300 million people in 16 countries. The country is also well-positioned to serve as a gateway to other markets in the region, including South Africa and Mozambique. While some road networks are still a work in progress and need to be rehabilitated, the distribution & logistics industry has taken off in the country, especially after COVID-19. Customers are more willing to order online and have their goods shipped to them than in previous years.

³⁴<https://knoema.com/atlas/Zimbabwe/topics/Education/Literacy/Adult-literacy-rate>

³⁵Education 5.0 is based on the idea that the fifth industrial revolution will be driven by artificial intelligence, robotics and other advanced technologies. The concept emphasizes the need for a new approach to education that prepares students for the challenges of the future.

Linkage among system actors

The extent of interactive linkages and learning can vary depending on a range of factors including the availability of resources and the willingness of the actors to collaborate and share knowledge. In recent years, there have been efforts to strengthen Zimbabwe's entrepreneurship ecosystem and improve linkages amongst actors. UNDP's Youth Connekt Project in collaboration with the Ministry of Youth, Sports, Arts & Culture brought together several enterprise-support organisations in search of the most innovative start-ups across all the 10 provinces of Zimbabwe for just over two months, where a number of actors was helpful. For instance for the private sector actors organizations such as Econet Wireless, CassavaSmartech, and Zimplats, have established various initiatives to support entrepreneurs. On the part of the academic institutions, innovation hubs and incubators have been set-up at nearly all the tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe. According to Matabvu of the Sunday Mail, the government disbursed ZWL\$42 million to the University of Zimbabwe (UZ), National University of Science and Technology (NUST) Marondera University of Science Education, Midlands State University (MSU), Chinhoyi University of Technology (CUT) and Harare Institute of Technology (HIT) to resource the hubs. This is because they are working on range of things, from researching on indigenous vegetables, indigenous trees and herbs, plant diseases, genetic testing and traditional grains (Matabvu, 2021). However, when asked about the success of innovation hubs at the tertiary institutions, respondents noted that while there is one that is notable - the Harare Institute of Technology - many of them focus on just one or two *rockstar* students while the rest obtain the more traditional knowledge-based degrees. The problem lies in the fact that the hubs are under-resourced and there is no real budget for Research & Development which drives innovators to migrate in order to successfully explore their innovations. Furthermore, vocational centers have also transformed into academic centers that produce degrees rather than the practical skills needed to produce innovative goods.

Other actors that support entrepreneurship in Zimbabwe include Non-governmental organizations, which provide support to entrepreneurs through training, mentorship, and access to funding. In Zimbabwe, organizations like Youth Entrepreneurs Zimbabwe (YEZ), Zimbabwe Women's Resource Centre and Network (ZWRCN), and the Zimbabwe National Chamber of Commerce (ZNCC) offer various services to support entrepreneurs.

And for foreigners, there are a range of support services, including the Zimbabwe Investment and Development Agency (ZIDA) and the Zimbabwe National Chamber of Commerce (ZNCC). These organizations provide information and advice on doing business in the country, as well as networking opportunities and access to local partners and stakeholders.

The above notwithstanding, there is still a lack of coordination among actors, and institutionalized organizations such as CZI are often excluded from enterprise-support initiatives in the start-up world. The participants interviewed also noted that every sector has its own group or sub-sections of connectivity and silos - often removed from the wider ecosystem. More needs to be done to create a vibrant and supportive ecosystem for entrepreneurs. When asked to rate Zimbabwe's innovation ecosystem on a scale of 1-10, none of the respondents scored it above 5.

Government policies and business environment

ICT policy

In Zimbabwe, there are policies and initiatives in place to promote innovation and entrepreneurship in the country. Included is the ICT policy, which aims to develop and promote the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) for socio-economic development and to improve the country's global competitiveness. The policy has several key objectives, including increasing access to affordable and reliable ICT infrastructure and services, promoting the development of local ICT industries and human resources, enhancing e-governance and public service delivery, and improving cyber security and data protection. This policy has enabled the rise in technology based entrepreneurship, particularly the use of mobile phones, which has created opportunities for digital innovation and entrepreneurship. The 2022 FinScope MSME Survey Report declares 81% of MSMEs use some form of technology in their business & some start-ups are now focused on developing mobile applications and other digital solutions that cater to the needs of Zimbabweans. 35% of MSMEs use digital financial services. However, Zimbabweans are for the most part consumers of new digital technologies rather than creators of it. Some respondents from the focus group discussion cited affordability as a contributing factor.

Business friendly environment and incentives

The government has implemented various measures to improve the business environment in Zimbabwe, including streamlining business registration and licensing procedures, reducing bureaucracy. However, more needs to be done to make the process more seamless and digital. For example, in the tourism industry a hotel license does not include a TV & liquor license. These need to be obtained separately & oftentimes at a different department which is inconvenient for entrepreneurs (Mawadza, 2023).

Zimbabwe also offers various investment incentives to attract foreign investors, including tax incentives, duty-free import of capital equipment, and reduced land rentals for industrial and commercial purposes. The government has also introduced duty-free capital import incentives for foreign investors in certain sectors, such as agriculture, tourism and renewable energy. Other incentives include Special Economic Zones (SEZs) to attract investment and promote economic growth in specific regions of the country. The SEZs offer various incentives to investors, including tax breaks, streamlined regulatory procedures, and infrastructure support.

4.4.3 Summary and concluding remarks

Zimbabwe has a population of approximately 15.1 million people, with the majority (61.4%³⁶) living in rural areas. With GDP per capita of around US \$1851 per capita, the country is

³⁶As reported in the National Financial Inclusion Strategy II Report

classified as a lower middle income country. In recent years the government is increasingly putting effort in national capacity in innovation and entrepreneurship with popular areas of focus being fintech, agriculture and ecommerce. However the country is facing following challenges in the development of the entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem development:

- i) **Finance:** Although there are a number of financial sources (including, Debt financing, private equity, grants, Export credit facilities) are available in Zimbabwe, most start-ups in the country struggle to secure funding. However, the funding challenge notwithstanding, the high culture of entrepreneurship in Zimbabwe enable many individuals to start their own businesses; and this culture is much higher for women than men. The major challenge that remains is that the ratio of necessity entrepreneurs versus opportunity entrepreneurs is high, and therefore the strong entrepreneurial culture might not amount to high growth and employment generating startups.
- ii) **Human capital:** The major Zimbabwean problem with human capital is brain drain: since 2000, with many skilled professionals leaving to seek better opportunities abroad. This has led to a shortage of skilled workers in certain sectors, particularly in healthcare and education. While Education reforms aims to address the dearth in technical & transferable skills, retaining talent is still difficult because remuneration & benefits levels are lower than in neighboring countries & further abroad.
- iii) **Access to markets:** According to those interviewed, access to markets is not a challenge to Zimbabwean entrepreneurs, as the country is part of the Southern African Development Community (SADC), a regional economic bloc that promotes trade and investment among member states. As a member of SADC, Zimbabwe has access to a market of over 300 million people in 16 countries.
- iv) **Linkage among system actors:** Although the ecosystem seems to be rich in terms of actors, the interaction between the actors is very weak. This is especially true for universities – while a number of innovation hubs are attached to the universities, many of the universities focus on just one or two *rockstar* students while the rest obtain the more traditional knowledge-based degrees. The problem lies in the fact that the hubs are under-resourced and there is no real budget for Research&Development, which can drive inventors to migrate in order to successfully explore their inventions.
- v) **Government policies and business environment:** Zimbabwean government has put in place conducive policies for entrepreneurship, e.g the ICT policy, which has enabled the rise in technology based entrepreneurship, particularly the use of mobile phones, which has created opportunities for digital innovation and entrepreneurship. The government has also implemented various measures to improve the business environment in Zimbabwe, including streamlining business registration and licensing procedures, reducing bureaucracy. However, more needs to be done to make entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem to perform efficiently, especially along strengthening of linkage among system actors.

4.5 Senegal

4.5.1 Social and economic context

Senegal covers an area of approximately 196,712 square kilometres (75,955 square miles) with a population of around 16.7 million people (2021 estimate). The country's GDP was around \$26.7 billion (nominal) or \$66.8 billion (PPP) in 2020. Senegal has enjoyed one of the highest GDP growth rates in the 15-member Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) over the last five years, with sustained economic growth rates averaging 6.5 per cent from 2014 through 2019, with The GDP per capita in Senegal was approximately \$1,611 (nominal) or \$4,040 (PPP) in 2020. Along with this income, is high level of unemployment: Unemployment remains a challenge in Senegal. The unemployment rate was around 15.4% in 2020, with higher rates among youth. Unfortunately, despite the investments, the human capital is not competitive enough, resulting from a poor educational system

Social indicators such as life expectancy are impressive for Senegal: The life expectancy at birth in Senegal was around 67.9 years for males and 70.7 years for females in 2020. Regarding education, Senegal has made progress in expanding access to education. The education system comprises primary, secondary, and tertiary levels; and a student has to spend 16 years going through the formal schooling system to the end. However, at the end of the long 16 years of schooling, one would still lack practical skills.

Regarding science, technology and innovation capabilities, Senegal – just like many African countries – is far behind. For instance, regarding R&D expenditure in Senegal is relatively low. The latest value from 2015 is 0.58 per cent. For comparison, the world average in 2015 based on 100 countries is 0.98 per cent.

Regarding startups, The startup ecosystem in Senegal has been growing steadily with an approximate number of 70 startups and raised around \$26m in the whole of 2021. However, the recent rise of Wave to the status of unicorn by raising 2 \$200 million has given a positive outlook to the success rates of startups in Senegal. The country has witnessed increased entrepreneurial activities, particularly in the technology, agriculture, and renewable energy sectors. The government has implemented initiatives for entrepreneurship and innovation, including incubation programs and funding opportunities.

4.5.2 Status of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems of Senegal

Finance

The local market for investment in Senegal is quite positive and inspiring. Indeed there are various types of funding available including equity (such as venture capital), debt capital, and philanthropic capital. One can cite Teranga Capital, Investisseurs & Partenaires (I&P), and Brightmore Capital among the investment funds and venture capital firms. The Senegalese government has also made efforts to enhance opportunities for funding by creating DER. The Délégation de l'Entrepreneuriat Rapide (DER), established in early 2018, aims to enhance the startup ecosystem and address the shortage of incubators and accelerators. DER has an Innovation Fund of 25 million USD over 5 years which accompanies entrepreneurs with tickets between 8,000 USD (incubation phase) and 100,000 USD (development phase). So far DER

has financially supported 260 startups. Furthermore, the construction of a science hub park in Diamniadio, located 35 km from Dakar, has set a precedent in support systems. With an investment of 70 million euros, the park will feature dedicated spaces for the public and private sectors, including private companies, incubators, teaching and research centres, and a Tier III data centre.

However, while Senegalese investors WIC Capital and Teranga Capital have made notable investments in Mburo and CAIF, respectively, most funding rounds have been predominantly led by foreign investors – primarily originating from the United States, France, and Mauritius. French multinational company Orange is a prominent supporter of entrepreneurship in Senegal. Orange operates as an investor through Orange Ventures, which invests in technology companies in Africa and the Middle East. However, in so doing, they foster digital inclusion, promoting innovation and entrepreneurship, and supporting the local digital ecosystem. Apart from these major funders, there are other financial organizations where startups could mobilize funding, including commercial banks, microfinance institutions, Development finance institutions such as the African Development Finance Bank (AfDB); government Agencies and initiatives, and Impact Investors and Philanthropic Organisations: Institutions such as the Tony Elumelu Foundation, Omidyar Network, Acumen, Ashoka, and the Global Innovation Fund focus on impact investing and philanthropy, providing funding and support to businesses with social or environmental objectives.

According to the interviews and focus group discussion, however - despite all the above available options, entrepreneurs in Senegal face several challenges when seeking funding for their ventures – given the large number of requests, available funding with no ties – such as the one by DER – is not enough at all. And while the incubators and accelerators have been helpful in capacity building, they don't give sufficient funds for people to actually start their own businesses.

Culture

Senegal has a growing culture of entrepreneurship, with increasing recognition and value placed on entrepreneurship in society. This – to a large extent – is the result of Senegal's growing digital infrastructure, youthful population with tech-savvy individuals, and entrepreneurial spirit of her young people. The government's active promotion of entrepreneurship and innovation through favorable policies such as the Start-up Act, support services and financial incentives with the creation of the Innovation Fund at the DER/FJ has contributed to this.

The above notwithstanding however – as explained in above - while there is a positive shift in the perception of entrepreneurship in Senegal, challenges still exists, such as limited access to capital, infrastructure, social expectations and regulatory barriers. The cultural aspect hindering innovation is also the lack of a culture of risk. There is a tendency to opt for safer initiatives. Moreover, there is no proper funding that would help test revolutionary ideas, similarly to the Silicon Valley system.

Human capital

Just like many other African countries, Senegal major education problem is theory based learning that does not provide skills for productive employment. According to the Minister of Employment, Vocational Training, Apprenticeship and Integration, Dame Diop, 200,000 young people arrive on the labour market in a year do not have skills or qualifications³⁷. This is despite the increase in school enrolment more generally and those that are specializing in scientific fields. In recent years, for instance, there has been an upsurge in the number of higher education institutions. Public universities in Senegal, such as UCAD (Cheikh Anta Diop University) in Dakar, UGB (Gaston Berger University) in Saint-Louis, provide access to education and contribute to the increase in the higher education enrollment rate, as well as the strengthening of the university network in Senegal. And the proportion of students enrolled in scientific streams increased from 22.5% in 2013 to 32% in 2017.

In trying to address the employment skill gap the government has tried to increase enrolment in vocational training. For instance it increased from 5.87% in 2012 to 8% in 2017. Additionally, efforts have been made to support young individuals in their professional careers, with the percentage of young leavers receiving assistance increasing from 29% in 2013 to 36% in 2017. Moreover, vocational training clusters have been implemented in sectors such as agriculture, poultry farming, and tourism sectors, promoting specialized skills and knowledge in these industries. The construction of training centers dedicated to building trades and mechanics further reinforces the emphasis on practical training and skill development. In addition, more and more universities or educational establishments have included specific modules for entrepreneurship and innovation. Others even have business incubation centres to offer students with a business project a framework and support to develop it. For example, one can cite the UASZ (AssaneSeck University of Ziguinchor) which has an incubator within it. In less than three years, the university produced more than 30 startups, predominantly in ICTs. The increasing return of more Senegalese who have gone to study abroad and are returning to serve their country is also helpful in increasing the number of experienced and skillful human capital. The above notwithstanding however, according to the interview, the challenges of mismatch between the skills acquired by university graduates and the needs of the labor market still lingers - as theory is prioritized over practice in most higher learning institutions.

Access to markets

Senegal has an [advantageous location](#) with major seaports that give easy access to European and North American markets. On land, the country shares borders with Mauritania, Mali, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, as well as the Gambia. Senegal also shares a maritime border with Cape Verde.

Support systems and interactive linkages

³⁷ <https://www.agenceecofin.com/formation/0812-83330-au-senegal-le-manque-de-competences-est-la-premiere-cause-du-chomage-des-jeunes>

The ecosystem of incubators and capacity-building entities for entrepreneurs in Senegal is vibrant and growing. Incubators are a huge part of the ecosystem as they organise workshops, seminars, and training sessions on various aspects of business development, such as market research, financial management, marketing, and pitching. Many incubators also collaborate on shared projects. There are different incubators that specialize in specific areas. For example, YeestalAgri Hub and Energy4Impact focus on agro-industry. In addition, Orange Digital Center and CTIC focus on technology and innovation. Among associations promoting innovation, one can cite the Blockchain Society Senegal, which brings blockchain enthusiasts, experts, and stakeholders together to discuss and implement blockchain-based solutions for social and economic development. Limited funding for implementation and a lack of monetary value are key gaps in Senegal's incubators, despite their strong focus on training and skills development. Entrepreneurs have access to multiple incubators for learning, but a lack of funding often hinders their progress, causing them to remain at the same stage without the means to grow their businesses.

The Agency for the Promotion of Investments and Exports (APIX) has also been very helpful in supporting entrepreneurs. APIX is the entity that has supported investors, Senegalese and foreigners, since the creation of the company in Senegal and throughout its activity. The mission of the Agency is to support business activity but also to promote the development of the country by improving the business climate, as well as by attracting investment in major infrastructure.

Other support system elements are physical infrastructure, where Senegal is doing very well. For instance Senegal has a dense and well-maintained road network that can ensure the smooth movement of people and goods. An urban mobility improvement program is underway to optimize travel to and within the capital. In addition to airports, Senegal has a well maintained railway systems; The Train Express Régional Dakar-AIBD (or TER Dakar-AIBD) is a standard gauge electric railway operating since 2022. It connects the capital of Dakar to Blaise-Diagne International Airport (AIBD). This project makes it possible to open up the capital, representing the major part of the country's activity, from the rest of Senegal and to move towards international railway networks.

Generally one can say the Senegalese ecosystem has good number of actors and elements, but the ecosystem actors do not necessarily work hand in hand. For example, there is little to no coordination between incubators/support systems and investors on the needs and support of the entrepreneur. In addition – according to the respondents – while the ecosystem actors add value to the entrepreneurs' journey, more funding and scaling opportunities are needed to boost them. For instance – as explained during the focus group discussion - there are too few accelerators and only a small number of startups were able to raise higher amounts of funding at an international level. There is also a missing link in the ecosystem: there is no habit of transmitting knowledge and starting new things from people who have worked with successful startups.

Government policies and business environment

The Senegalese government has recently shown a growing interest in developing entrepreneurship and foreign investment in Senegal. Thanks to the article no. 2008-29 of 28

July 2008 by the Senegalese government which stipulates the rules and regulations around start-ups in Senegal, the ecosystem has become more institutionalized. Moreover, in terms of innovation, the government has pushed for Digital Senegal 2025, which has led to the establishment of the Start-up Act. Business registration process has also been made much easier - Since November 2007, entrepreneurs can register at the one-stop shop, which takes care of what was formerly done in seven different procedures; and In Senegal, forming a foreign-owned limited liability company (LLC) takes five procedures and ten days (Dakar). This is one of the fastest processes in Sub-Saharan Africa, much faster than the IAB global average. Senegal has an Investment Code that incentivizes local and foreign investors. The code offers benefits such as tax exemptions, customs duties relief, and facilitation of administrative procedures for eligible businesses.

However, with all this good things, According to the interviews, bottlenecks and challenges still exist within the business environment, including bureaucratic procedures, lengthy registration processes, and difficulties accessing finance.

4.5.3 Summary and concluding remarks

Senegal, a relatively smaller country of around 16.7 million people, is one of the fastest growing African countries with sustained economic growth rates averaging 6.5 per cent from 2014 through to 2019. Looking at government's efforts in terms of infrastructure and policies for building entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem, one note a much more impressive picture compared to other four markets studied. Resounding progress has especially been made in sectors such as fintech, e-logistics, and mobility, in a way that might be even better than in the European ecosystem. However, despite this impressive picture, some stumbling blocks still remain, including:

- i) Inadequate funding for both the accelerators and startups
- ii) Rote learning: the education system prioritizes theory over practice, which in turn affects the quality of the job market. While cheap labour can be a positive side, quality is compromised.
- iii) The culture of risk averseness is also a big problem in Senegal.
- iv) The ecosystem elements are not properly working – while the system seems to be rich in terms of actors, the actors are not properly coordinated to enable productive entrepreneurship and innovation. For instance there is little to no coordination between incubators/support systems and investors on the needs and support of the entrepreneur,

5. General African outlook of entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem

This section is an attempt to paint a general picture of the African entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystems, basically looking at challenges and opportunities. The section tries to bring together the experiences of the five countries discussed above, buttressed by the experience from elsewhere in the continent – basically following the same structure as in the countries' cases.

5.1 Social and economic context

With exception of few countries' specific differences, the general social, economic and cultural characteristic relevant for entrepreneurship and innovation, are fairly the same across the five project countries and elsewhere in Africa: most of the African countries have good growth; for instance in the five years to 2015, when many nations were still staggering from the global economic crisis, Africa's GDP grew at 3.3% a year – faster than the world average (World Economic Forum, 2017)³⁸. Africa is also rich in natural resources with ample opportunities to add value to. Many of the countries' population is youthful with number of unemployed rapidly increasing. The continent has one of the youngest populations, which is set to double by 2050, with most participating in vulnerable employment³⁹ that can easily be turned into decent jobs if good policies are put in place. In fact this is already happening as young people are increasing turning to startups.

The good thing is that the countries are also increasingly investing in education, with major challenge around theory based rote learning, with little opportunities for practical experience. As many of the interviewed put it, it is a theory based education for all the studied countries. Given this, although startups are mushrooming in most of the African countries, including the five markets, most of these are just means of survival, rather than growth oriented enterprises. Although this type of enterprises provides an important source of income for many, it does not typically increase productivity and investment in local economies, nor spur the growth required to drastically increase prosperity in African countries⁴⁰. For the studied countries, many of the more serious and technology oriented startups are in the areas of fintech, agriculture and ecommerce. However, according to the existing studies – including this one – many of the African countries' startups do not survive beyond five years. One of the study indicated that Ethiopia and Rwanda has the highest failure rate of 75%, followed by Ghana with 71%, and

³⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/startup-landscape-africa-challenges-opportunities>

³⁹ https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2015/08/what-are-the-biggest-challenges-for-africas-entrepreneurs/?DAG=3&qad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAiA98WrBhAYEiwA2WvhOgN38li99m74PzC7sS3tmrbl60myWfzqCVPZeWm6oaw8LRRck7XFMhOCstkQAvD_BwE

⁴⁰ https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2015/08/what-are-the-biggest-challenges-for-africas-entrepreneurs/?DAG=3&qad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAiA98WrBhAYEiwA2WvhOgN38li99m74PzC7sS3tmrbl60myWfzqCVPZeWm6oaw8LRRck7XFMhOCstkQAvD_BwE

Uganda with 70%. On the other hand, Kenya had the lowest failure rate of 24%, followed by South Africa with 28%, and Nigeria with 29%⁴¹.

In terms of investment in science, technology and innovation (STI) – apart from South Africa – many of the African countries invest very little in STI. Generally, [only 1% of global investment in R&D](#) is spent in Africa and the continent earns only 0.1% of patents. This is despite the fact that the continent houses about 15% of the World's population (World Economic Forum, 2017)⁴²

5.2 Status of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems of Africa

Finance

Finance is one of the top challenges of entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems for all the five studied markets. And this is the case for most of the existing studies on Africa. This is despite the fact that one of the most noticeable trends in the African startup landscape is the rapid growth of funding. According to Google's 2021 Africa Developer Ecosystem report, African startups raised more than \$4.3 billion in 2021 from local and international investors. That's two and a half times the year before⁴³. According to a report by the United Nations Technology Bank, some of these challenges include⁴⁴:

- i. Lack of local investors: Most of the funding for African startups comes from foreign investors, who may have different expectations, preferences, and more risk averse than local ones. Moreover, foreign investors may not have sufficient knowledge or networks in the local markets, which may limit their ability to provide mentorship or connections to African startups.
- ii. Lack of later-stage funding: the report explains that while early-stage funding has increased significantly in recent years, later-stage funding remains scarce and competitive. As a result, many African startups struggle to scale up or exit successfully. From our study however, it seems the funding is available for the later than the earlier stages, e.g. for South Africa and Tanzania. I think by earlier stages what is meant in the Technology Bank study, is the ideation stage, which our study also indicated better funding here, with serious limitation at the middle stage of market testing, e.g. for Tanzania.
- iii. Lack of diversity: The funding landscape in Africa is dominated by male founders and investors, who tend to favor male-led startups. Only 13 percent of active investors in Africa are female.

One of the evident characteristics of the African startups funding is that, it largely comes from outside the continent in terms of grants and multinational – at least this is the findings of the

⁴¹<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/startup-landscape-africa-challenges-opportunities>

⁴²<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2017/05/scientists-are-the-key-to-africas-future/>

⁴³<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/startup-landscape-africa-challenges-opportunities>

⁴⁴<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/startup-landscape-africa-challenges-opportunities>

five market for this study; the exception being South Africa. And this to a large extent is a result of very small number of large companies in most African countries.

Human capital

According to the current five countries' study, countries are generally doing very well in terms of expanding opportunities for education, including recent introduction of entrepreneurship curriculum in tertiary education and establishment of incubators around universities. This notwithstanding, a number of challenges have been mentioned, including theory based learning that does not provide for opportunities for skills building. Another, mentioned challenge is brain drain (Zimbabwe, Ghana and South Africa) - attributed to the higher wages, better opportunities, and a higher standard of living elsewhere in the world – especially the Western rich countries. The challenge of brain drain affecting Africa's entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem has also been echoed elsewhere – as Ebikara Spiff writes, “many skilled professionals leave the continent in search of better opportunities. And therefore suggest tech startups to be creative in recruiting and retaining talent, offering competitive salaries and unique incentives”⁴⁵. The problem of brain drain also causes inadequacy of the experienced mentors for the startups.

Poor human capital is also affecting the performance of incubators and accelerators which are very important system actors as they support entrepreneurs and startups in so many ways. But according to those interviewed, the managers and employees of these structure do not have experience in business development and thus are not that helpful in mentoring the startups.

Access to markets

Apart from Tanzania and South Africa, access to markets by startups has not been expressed as a major concern. For South Africa – as explained in the country case above – lack of access to a sizable market due to the local market being small (for rapidly increasing number of startups) and the neighboring ones being so different, making it difficult for startups to grow and expand. The above notwithstanding however, challenges around markets in rest of Africa is well documented in existing information. One major problem being weak local markets – it is problematic to serve consumers with limited purchasing power, with the problem being compounded by poor marketing strategies, which is part of general poor entrepreneurial knowledge and skills. African startups struggle to effectively market and brand their products or services, which result in poor visibility, low customer engagement, and ultimately, failure⁴⁶. Another major market challenges for African startups is access to export markets. Many SMEs in developing countries – especially in Africa – are unable to export their products due to a lack of knowledge about international markets, or lack of resources or support to navigate the

⁴⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/scaling-tech-startup-africa-overcoming-unique-challenges-spiff>

⁴⁶ <https://leatherback.co/blog-and-news/blogs/problems-facing-african-startups-today/>

complex regulations and logistics involved in exporting⁴⁷. But also poor quality of products – given poor science and technology inputs – can be another major problem, especially during this era of rapid technological change.

System actors and support infrastructure

While those interviewed in the five countries' case studies did not mention infrastructure as a major challenge, many secondary sources has indicated good infrastructure as one of the major challenge for many of the African startups. For instance, Ernst & Young's report on "Addressing Africa's Infrastructure Deficit" shows that the biggest infrastructure deficits in Africa are in power and roads. In a CNN article, it was identified that the whole of Sub-Saharan Africa generates roughly the same amount of electricity as Spain, despite having a population of 800 million people⁴⁸. May be what this report overlooked in such comparison is the fact that demand for power is very much proportional to the level of industrialization of a country, where Africa is at the bottom – and very far from the rich and industrialized countries such as those in Europe.

Regarding knowledge infrastructure (supportive system actors), the five case studies indicate presence of most of the important actors, including incubators and accelerators, universities and research centers, Angel investors, Venture capitalists, Governments and startups themselves. However, the challenge is in weak incubators and accelerators, absence of large local corporations, and the interaction between and among the system actors. For incubators and accelerators the capacity problem is compounded by lack of the overall coordinator of the hubs as expressed in the five countries case. Existing literature also echoes the problem, where it is indicated that the ecosystem lacks structure to track hubs' activities, to understand what programme exists in the ecosystem and how each hub can align systematically to complement each other, rather than duplicating efforts.

The challenge around linkage between and among system actors is dearth of information on this: those interviewed by the project in the five project countries, either did not say anything on this, or expressed very inadequate linkage among systems actors, with those between knowledge organizations and startups being seriously weak. Literature search also indicated very little, apart from the information that a good number of incubators belong to the universities, which themselves are not doing well in producing well performing startups. According to existing information, challenges around university based incubators include, lack of mixing of students from economic and business studies with students from other faculties and with different backgrounds and therefore establishing strong start-up groups; and more generally, there is no accurate cooperation between university, government and industry, and therefore no clear policies to enable these structures at the university to work properly (Hassan, 2020). The exception being some universities in Egypt and South Africa, such as the University

⁴⁷<https://www.westfordonline.com/blogs/challenges-faced-by-entrepreneurship-and-msmes-in-developing-countries/>

⁴⁸<https://thearodong.medium.com/why-african-startups-fail-4f2755d137a3>

of Cape Town (UCT), which – according to the source – its success is based on the fact that the University provides access to startup ideation initiatives, incubation facilities, and connecting students with the broader Cape Town startup ecosystem⁴⁹.

Another major problem with the African entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem actors is the fact that African countries have very inadequate large companies (corporations). Apart from supporting startups financially, corporations help startups indirectly by attracting talent to a city and also providing many platforms and opportunities for startup entrepreneurs to connect and network. Apart from this – as explained in the conceptual framework – it is the experienced employees of these organizations that become founders of new and well performing companies. Existing studies indicate that a startup without a corporate backer appears two times more likely to fail than a company that has had at least one such investor on its cap table. There are several potential reasons that corporate-backed companies have higher survival rates. Two on top are⁵⁰:

- i) Corporate investors have better due diligence, especially when it comes to more technical companies. For instance the expertise for hiring the right technical team, their understanding of the challenges of bringing a product to the market, and their understanding of the IP strategy
- ii) Simply being backed by a corporation helps validate a startup, which can make it easier to raise further funding. Many investors take comfort from the idea of a strategically aligned corporate, which understands the market, being invested

Absence of these large corporations in Africa must have contributed to the observed weaknesses of the African startups.

Government policies and business environment

As indicated in the five country cases, many African governments has implemented various initiatives to support and encourage the growth of small businesses and medium-sized enterprises. However, despite this – as explained in the five country cases studies -founders generally face regulatory and financial huddles when trying to bring new and innovative ideas to market, largely because of inadequate implementation of policies. „Bureaucracy in business registration has also been expressed as one of the major challenges to doing business in the five countries case. More generally in Africa – as indicated in literature - many African countries have complex and often unpredictable regulatory environments, which can be challenging for startups to navigate. Startups may face delays in obtaining necessary licenses and permits, and may also be subject to unpredictable changes in regulations or policies that can impact their operations⁵¹. This problem seem to be compounded by the fact that the connection between

⁴⁹<https://techcabal.com/2023/08/14/uct-tech-startup-ceos/>

⁵⁰*Global Corporate venturing: lventing.com/corporate/corporate-backed-startups-are-more-likely-to-survive/*

⁵¹<https://thearodong.medium.com/why-african-startups-fail-4f2755d137a3>

startups and the structures that supports them, with policy makers seems to be sporadic and many of the interviewed entrepreneurs are not aware of the existence of the policies that potentially supports them.

There is also not only lack of support for innovative startups when they try to come up with new products, but actually blockage as indicated in the Tanzania case for new products for digital financial services.

6. Concluding remarks and policy recommendation

6.1 Concluding remarks

As indicated in the five country cases and elsewhere in Africa, the general social economic characteristic of the region is relevant to entrepreneurship and innovation: most countries have good growth, rich in natural resources that needs value adding, and many of the countries' population is youthful with number of unemployed rapidly increasing. In addition, the fact that there is a critical need for innovative solutions to address many of the social and economic challenges, such limited access to healthcare and education facing the continent, is also a breeding ground for entrepreneurship and innovativeness. Luckily, African governments are increasingly being aware of such potentials of startups and innovation, and have begun to put in place policies and programs to support the entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems in their countries.

The above notwithstanding however, African entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem is faced by myriad of challenges. The most serious include the following:

- i. **Finance:** access to finance, especially funding for market testing of new products is a serious problem. And the little that is available is largely from the foreign sources who might not know the local market quite well, and therefore less appetite to invest in African startups.
- ii. **Human capital:** although many African governments have expanded opportunities for schooling – for the primary, secondary and tertiary levels, there is a major challenges of lack of experiential learning as most the curriculum are based on theory learning; as a result those who start business do not have adequate knowledge on how to run successful startups. Lack of skilled personnel also affects the performance of incubators and accelerators who are the major support structures for the startups. For the few available experienced personnel, there is a problem of brain drain.
- iii. **Access to markets:** One major problem of African startups is weak local markets – it is problematic to serve consumers with limited purchasing power. This problem is compounded by poor marketing strategies and skills in accessing export markets by the startups. Of course quality of products – resulting from low tech inputs – is also an issue for the export markets.
- iv. **Adequacy of system actors and strengths of interactive linkage:** While for most of the five countries cases studies, most of the important system elements are available (with exception of local corporate organizations, angel investors and venture capital), their strengths and interactive linkage is questionable; and very unfortunately there is no adequate information on this. According to the little information available, linkage among most system actors, especially with knowledge organizations, is very weak – leading to massive failures in startups. And for those with adequate linkage, e.g. between startups and incubators and accelerators, there is problem of capacity. Most of the existing incubators and accelerators do not have capacity to adequately mentor the startups.

- v. **Government policies and business environment:** Although many of the African governments have all sorts of policies to enable entrepreneurship and innovation, these seem to have little impact on the lives of businesses because the policies are rarely implemented. Additionally, bureaucracy seems another major problem for the business environment. This is a major problem, because all other mentioned problems have their solution rooted in good and implemented policies, and conducive business environment.

6.2 Recommendations

- a) **Policy Implementation:** Policy and good business environment is everything when it comes to success of a business – whether small or big. African governments are urged not only to promulgate good policies, but also to implement them and learn from implementation for further improvement.
- b) **Supporting local investors (large companies):** African governments should promulgate good innovation policies and provide conducive business environment, not only for the startups, but also for the established and large companies, which have a critical role to play in the local entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems.
- c) **Diversifying funding sources:** Besides venture capital and Angel investors, African startups can explore alternative sources of funding, such as crowdfunding, bootstrapping, revenue-based financing, or grants. These sources can offer more flexibility, affordability, or accessibility for different types of startups. Ways have to be found to enable startups access these funds – business training being one.
- d) **Further research:** this exercise has brought to our attention that, there are very limited in-depth high quality studies on the African entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem; one of the major recommendations is therefore to adequately study the system - the study on the strengths and interactive linkage among system actors is extremely important and urgent.

References

- ANDE (2021). Financial Constraints to Entrepreneurs in Ghana
- Alliance for African Partnership (2022). Youth Entrepreneurial Ecosystem for Sustainable Development in Sub-Saharan Africa
- Audretsch, D. B., & Belitski, M. (2017). Entrepreneurial ecosystems in cities: establishing the framework conditions. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 42, 1030-1051. DOI: 10.1007/s10961-016-9473-8. Available at <https://centaur.reading.ac.uk/61156/>
- Davidsson, P., Achtenhagen, L. & L. Naldi. (2007). “What Do We Know About Small Firm Growth?” In: Simon Parker (ed.), *The Life Cycle of Entrepreneurial Ventures*, New York: Springer 361–398.
- Disrupt Africa (2022). The South African Startup Ecosystem Report 2022 & Full Startup
- Diyamett and Mwigusa (2023), “Digital innovation ecosystem development for financial inclusion and market access in a context of a poor country: the case of Tanzania”. Research report, STIPRO & AERC, Dar es Salaam.
- Granstrand O., & Holgersson, M. (2020). Innovation ecosystems: A conceptual review and a new definition. *Technovation*, 90, 102098. DOI: 10.1016/j.technovation.2019.102098
- HDIF (ND). Catalysing and scaling Innovation in Tanzania: A review of approaches
- Hassan, N. A. (2020). University business incubators as a tool for accelerating entrepreneurship: theoretical perspective. *Review of Economics and Political Science*
- International Trade Center & COSTECH (ND). Tech Entrepreneurship Ecosystem in Tanzania: Network Analysis and Mapping of Institutions Supporting Entrepreneurship
- Kraemer-Mbula, Erika, Gussai Sheikheldin and Rungano Karimanzira. 2021. ‘Southern Africa’ in *UNESCO Science Report: the Race Against Time for Smarter Development*. Schneegans, S., T. Straza and J. Lewis (eds). Paris: UNESCO Publishing
- Kuratko, D.F. & M.R. Hodgetts. (2001). *Entrepreneurship: A Contemporary Approach*, Orlando, FL: The Dryden Press, Harcourt Brace College Publishers.
- Ianioglo, A. (ND). Innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystems, In *Innovation, Research and Development and Capital Evaluation*. *IntechOpen*
- Lam, P. T., & Law, A. O. (2016). Crowdfunding for renewable and sustainable energy projects: An exploratory case study approach. *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 60, 11-20.
- Low, M.B. & I.C. MacMillan. (1988). “Entrepreneurship: Past Research and Future Challenges”, *Journal of Management*, 14(2), 139–161.
- Mack, E., & Mayer, H. (2016). The evolutionary dynamics of entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Urban studies*, 53(10), 2118-2133. DOI: 10.1177/0042098015586547
- Maher, Hamid, Abdeljabbar Chraïti, Anas Laabi, Takeshi Oikawa, Tolu Oyekan, and Andrew Bosson. “[Igniting Innovation-Based Growth in Africa.](#)” *BCG*, OCTOBER 15, 2021

- Matabvu, Debra. (2021). Innovation hubs get \$42m. The Sunday Mail. <https://www.sundaymail.co.zw/innovation-hubs-get-42m>
- MattiaFosci et al, (2019). Assessing the needs of the research system in Tanzania. Report for the SRIA programme. The UK Department for International Development
- OECD. 2018. Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation.
- Schumpeter, J.A. (1934). The Theory of Economic Development, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Sergi, B., Babcock, M., Williams, N. J., Thornburg, J., Loew, A., & Ciez, R. E. (2018). Institutional influence on power sector investments: A case study of on-and off-grid energy in Kenya and Tanzania. *Energy research & social science*, 41, 59-70.
- Stam, E. (2015). Entrepreneurial ecosystems and regional policy: a sympathetic critique. *European planning studies*, 23(9), 1759-1769. DOI: 10.1080/09654313.2015.1061484
- Stevenson HH, JarilloMossi JC (1986). Preserving entrepreneurship as companies grow. *Journal of Business Strategy*. 1986;7(1):10-23
- World Bank. (2017). *Tech Start-up Ecosystem in Dar es Salaam: Findings and Recommendations*. World Bank.

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